

SECURITY CHALLENGES AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The general aim of this paper was to evaluate the economic consequences of insecurity in Nigeria with the huge expenditures on security and defense as a relevant proxy for insecurity; while the specific objectives the study were to examine effects of insecurity on food production with agricultural GDP as a proxy, poverty level with per capita income as a proxy and economic development with annual expenditures on education as a proxy. Annual data on agricultural GDP, expenditures on security and defense, expenditures on education and income per capita sourced through National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Annual Reports and Accounts, and various other sources were used for this study. Inferential statistical tool of analysis for this study was Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique. The result of the analysis indicated that expenditures on defense and security had no significant effect on education. Security situation in Nigeria, annual expenditures on security and defense as a proxy had significant negative effect on food production, agricultural GDP as a proxy. Security situation had significant negative effect on poverty level in Nigeria with income per capita as a proxy for poverty. Implications of the findings: the negative effect of the security situation in Nigeria on agricultural production implies that if insecurity is not combated may result in food hunger and frustrate Nigeria from accomplishing Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of zero hunger in 2030 among other implications.*

Keywords: *Security Challenges, Economic Growth.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The root causes of insecurity in Nigeria have linked to the ways the country was colonized at pre – independence and governed after independence. Other factors that have shaped the security situation of Nigeria are injustice, inequity, lack of fair play, flagrant abuses of power, bad governance, institutional weakness, multi- ethnicity and severe stress on basic resources. Colonial policies of uneven development, ethnic ranking/ stratification and discrimination nurtured the level of insecurity in Nigeria today. Ethnic ranking/ stratification and discrimination by the British style of governance gave rise to deep-rooted socio-political disharmony, mutual suspicion and strife, after

independence. Efforts to reverse and to maintain the status quo have resulted in kidnapping/ adoption, terrorism, constant bloodletting and acute insecurity in Nigeria (Achebe 2004; Todaro& Smith 2012).

The Nigeria-Biafra civil war partly contributed to state of insecurity in Nigeria. It was at the end of the civil war that armed robbery began in Nigeria. The inability of the country to carry out appreciable disarmament, cleansing of land mines, lethal weapons and explosives resulted in proliferation of weapons, violent crimes and general insecurity as weapons entered wrong hands (Aja 2018; Igwe, 2018; Ezeibe, 2021; Ezeani, 2021; Ani&Ezeibe, 2022). Other factors that contributed to insecurity especially in the south- south part of Nigeria are resource control and environmental decay caused by oil drilling (Asiwaju, 1984; Dioka, 1997; Chukwu, 2007; Egbo, 2001).

The inability of the Hausa people to check the magnitude of Fulani political and, cultural, influence in the North is the main cause of insecurity in the North. For instance, they allowed the Fulani people to establish their rule over the initial independent states of the Hausa, Birom, Anga, Nupe, Tiv, and Yoruba of Ilorin after demolishing free monarchical institutions of the afore mentioned independent states, imposing on them an Islamic and feudalistic oriented rule. Later the Fulani rule replaced the former traditional rulers with members of their own clan as rulers styled emirs (Ademoyega, 1981; Achebe, 2004; Igwe, 2018). Efforts by the Fulani nation to maintain leadership has been the cause of insecurity in Nigeria, especially in the North.

These scenarios have developed several tentacles like an octopus. For instance, the gradual but steady move to maintain Islamic and feudalistic rule in Nigeria marked the beginning of Boko Haram and insurgency in the Northern Nigeria. In 2002, Mohammed Yusuf, an Islamic religious teacher in Maiduguri established Boko Haram. He later moved the group moved to Kanumma in Yobe state close to Niger republic border where Yusuf set up his base and named it Afghanistan. The group is often referred to as Nigerian Taliban (Oyingibo& Raymond 2021; Education for All Global Monitoring Reports, 2010). This terrorist Islamic group has abducted millions of Nigerians for ransom, destroyed properties worth of trillion -naira. It has made farming in the North a risky venture as whoever is engaging in it is risking abduction or death. More importantly, this group has destroyed destinies of young girls in the Northern Nigeria as evidenced by the abduction of chibok girls. The group has ambushed and murdered several thousands of Nigerians and rendered children and women orphans and widows (Igwe, 2018; Aja, 2018). Today Nigeria ranks first among African countries in terms of level of insecurity (World Bank, 2022).

The depressive effect of the large wealth expended on fighting insecurity on economic growth in Nigeria is the concern of this paper. Nigeria tops the list of countries with the highest in Africa with the defense spending of \$5.8 billion in 2022. By July 2022, Nigeria borrowed N722.53 billion from domestic capital market to fight insecurity. The country also borrowed \$39.58 from the World Bank. The senate, civil society organizations and security stakeholders have expressed worries over rising

internal security and defense budgets in the last decades above N8trillion despite the declining impacts of such budgetary votes on the country's security situation (World Bank, 2022; Stewart, 2021; United Nation Development Programs, 2021). In 2016, the country spent 0.43% of her GDP on procurement of security arms, which rose to 2.2% in 2022(World Bank, 2020). The huge budget on internal security and defense in Nigeria is beginning to raise relevant questions over the country's capacity to meet Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2030. There is fear that the rising security expenditure may have depressed expenditures on agriculture and education to result in shortage and food scarcity and in Nigeria. Therefore, the objectives of this paper are to examine the effect of rising insecurity on Poverty level, education, and agricultural output in Nigeria. The variables for this study are security and defense expenditures, per capita income- a relevant proxy for poverty, agricultural output – a relevant proxy for hunger and budgetary expenditures on education- a relevant proxy for quality of education. It is therefore hypothesized that rising expenditure on security and defense has significant negative effects on poverty level, agriculture, and annual budgetary expenditures on education in Nigeria.

2.0 CONCEPTUAL ISSUES

Physical security is the foundation for human capabilities. It reflects freedom from dangers of losing lives, liberty and property. Fundamentally, insecurity can be traced to the variables for this study are security and defense expenditures, per capita income- a relevant proxy for poverty, agricultural output – a relevant proxy for hunger and budgetary expenditures on education- a relevant proxy for quality of education. It is therefore hypothesized that rising expenditure on security and defense has significant negative effects on poverty level, agriculture, and annual budgetary expenditures on education in Nigeria.

Security reflects freedom from conflict, armed aggression, wars, insurgency, abduction, kidnapping, militancy, and all sorts of violent crimes against humanity. In this study, security implies annual budgetary allocations and expenditures on security and defense. The wisdom here is that these expenditures and allocations capture the magnitude of security challenges. Education in this study implies annual budgetary to education, with the wisdom that well-funded education improves the standard of education, quality of skill and entire human productive assets. Agriculture in this study implies agricultural GDP annually in Nigeria. And standard of living or poverty level is measured in terms of income per capita which is GDP per population of a given country. All these are core issues of development in Nigeria. Economic development is improvement in the quality of human lives in terms of capabilities, levels of living, self-esteem, freedom and literacy level (Todaro & Smith, 2011). It implies improved food supply, wide range of choices goods and services, creation of employment, improved literacy level, and human capital development. Sustainable development is meeting the needs of the present generation without compromising the needs of the future generations. Expenditures to fight insecurity in Nigeria appear to have depressed budgetary allocations to the

critical sectors. Hence, state of education, security, agriculture and poverty level determine the capacity of a country to accomplish sustainable development. General insecurity may destroy the existing infrastructure and divert the attention of the state towards procurement of arms, resulting in the distortion of budgetary allocations to human and social capital development resulting poor growth and development.

3.0 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical Frame Work

To accomplish the objectives of this paper in terms of theoretical basis, the author adapted sociological, traditional, and structural theories of conflict to capture the Nigerian experience. According to sociological perspective, insecurity prevents individuals and groups from meeting their needs and expectations in terms of business activities. According to the structural theory, problem of insecurity is built into particular ways societies are structured and organized in terms of political and economic structures. Countries that witness political and economic exclusion, injustice, corruption, poverty, inequity, and political illegitimacy suffer acute suffer acute insecurity and problem of economic development (Aja-Akpuru –Aja, 2007).

Development-Security Linkages

Insecurity can distort the production function as it depresses investment in productive assets (human and physical assets). In line with Cobb-Douglas production function, production of output requires infrastructure or capital, skilled and unskilled labor which are presented as:

$Q = F(K, L^S + L^U) \dots \dots \dots (2.1)$

K represents infrastructure; L^S , represents skilled labor ; L^U represents unskilled labour.

K, L^S , and L^U are improved by education, improved health. It discourages investment, entrepreneurship and accelerates brain drain. General insecurity may destroy the existing infrastructure and divert the attention of the state towards procurement of arms, resulting in the distortion of budgetary allocations to human and social capital development resulting poor growth and development. Insecurity introduces uncertainties in investment opportunities (Ezeibe, 2021; Udo, Ishaku & Ndubuaku, 2020). The level of expenditures to maintain internal security and defense appears to have risen astronomically to depress expenditures on education. Rising insecurity implies rising security budgets and declining budgets for all sorts of capital investment. IMF studies on eight countries found that insecurity can cause education spending fall at the rate of -4.3% per person per year. Again, there is fear that rising expenditures on internal security and defense have depressed expenditures on education.

$Educ... = f(SEC) \dots \dots \dots (2.2)$

$Educ = \alpha_0 + SEC \alpha_1 + \varepsilon_1 \dots \dots \dots (2.3)$

Economic harm from insecurity holds back investment including investment in agriculture, growth and development to worsen the level of poverty.

$$\text{Agric.} = f(\text{SEC}) \dots \dots \dots (2.4)$$

$$\text{Agric.} = \alpha_0 + \text{SEC} \alpha_1 + \varepsilon_1 \dots (2.5)$$

Agric is annual agricultural production; α_0 is intercept; α_1 is coefficient of SEC. It worsens poverty level. Decision rule: $\alpha_1 > 0$ at 5 or less than 5% of significance implies that security situation supports improved education or agriculture otherwise it depresses them in Nigeria.

$$\text{Percap} = f(\text{sec.}) \dots \dots (2.6),$$

Where sec is annual expenditures on security, percap is income per capita.

$$\text{percap} = \alpha_0 + \text{SEC} \alpha_1 + \varepsilon_1 \dots \dots (2.7)$$

Note: poverty influences insecurity and insecurity affects poverty, hence

$$\text{SEC} = \alpha_0 + \text{Percap} \alpha_1 + \varepsilon_1 \dots \dots \dots (2.8).$$

α_0 Is the intercept. α_1 Is the coefficient of percapita income; ε_1 is the error term. There is fear in Nigeria that the rising expenditures on internal security and defense would have depressed investment in education. Decision Rule: $\alpha_1 > 0$ at 5% or less than 5% of significance implies that security situation supports living standard otherwise it depresses it in Nigeria.

3.2 Methodology

Methodology for this paper is purely econometrics involving statement of theory, specification of model, obtaining of data, estimation of empirical model, hypothesis testing and forecasting. Secondary data were used for this study. The study employed annual time series data from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), CBN Annual Reports and Accounts, World Bank and various sources. To estimate equations 2.3, 2.5, 2.7 and 2.8, Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method was employed.

4.0 Presentation and Analysis of Results

Table 4.1: ARDL Test Result

Dependent Variable: Edu

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-statistic	Probability
Edu(-1)	0.860743	0.100679	8.54931	0.00000
SEC	0.114753	0.124008	0.925367	0.36664
C	30.78878	34.90627	0.882042	0.38888

Source: Researcher’s Compilation

R-Squared	0.793633	mean dependent Var	260.1935
Adj.R-Squared	0.77197	S.D dependent Var	10.5443
S.E Regression	62.31822	Akaike Infor Criterion	11.22851
Sum Squared Resid	73787.65	Schwartz Infor Criterion	11.37729

Log Likelihood	-120.5136	Hannan-Quin Criterion	11.26356
F-Statistic	36.54794	Durbin-Watson Statistic	2.120000
Prob(Stat)	0.00000		

Table 4.2: ARDL Test Result between agriculture and security

Dependent Variable: Agric

Methodology: ARDL

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-stat	Probability
Agric(-1)	0.918288	0.073246	12.5769	0.0000
SEC	-0.335988	0.0116718	2.00966	0.0057
C	-0.474354	3.9981478	-0.11864	0.9068

Source: Researcher's Computation

Squared	0.932218	mean dependent Var	148.8847
Adj.R-Squared	0.877993	S.D dependent Var	118.1887
S.E Regression	41.282615	Akaike Infor Criterion	10.5885
Sum Squared Resid	17042.641	Schwartz Infor Criterion	11.03165
Log Likelihood	-91.535077	Hannan-Quin Criterion	10.6600
F-Statistic	17.191500	Durbin-Watson Statistic	2.47701
Prob(Stat)	0.00067		

Table 4.3: ARDL Test Result between poverty and security

Methodology: ARDL

Dependent Variable: Per capita Income

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-Stat	Probability
Percapita(-1)	0.695933	0.097255	7.55787	0.0000
SEC	2.065127	0.779114	2.650610	1.0212
SEC(-1)	-0.450799	1.036636	-0.434868	0.6714
SEC(-2)	-1.019723	1.001123	-1.018579	0.3285
SEC(-3)	-0.633771	0.996733	-0.025815	0.5432
SEC(-4)	-1.973599	0.836371	-2.359718	0.0361
C	373.3562	173.1070	2.156795	0.0520

Source: Researcher's Computation

Squared	0.91071	mean dependent Var	33.70682
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Adj.R-Squared	0.866071	S.D dependent Var	20.28203
S.E Regression	195.6168	Akaike Infor Criterion	7.22851
Sum Squared Resid	1334.641	Schwartz Infor Criterion	7.37729
Log Likelihood	-76.37577	Hannan-Quin Criterion	7.26356
F-Statistic	78.63500	Durbin-Watson Statistic	1.9717
Prob(Stat)	0.00000		

Table: 4.4: ARDL Test Result between security and Poverty level

Dependent Variable: SEC

Methodology: ARDL

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t- Stat	Probability
SEC(-1)	-0.049059	0.274997	-0.178399	0.8620
SEC(-2)	0.149687	0.231619	0.632608	0.5412
SEC(-3)	0.385941	0.231336	1.668341	0.1262
Percap	0.112944	0.045590	2.477361	0.0327
Percap(-1)	0.072135	0.064911	1.111286	0.2924
Percap((-2)	-0.045658	0.063608	-0.717600	0.4893
Percap(-3)	-0.054408	0.065773	-0.827200	0.4274
Percap(-4)	-0.083446	0.054223	-1.538990	0.0048
C	32.39917	41.04614	0.7899335	0.4482

Squared	0.91071	mean dependent Var	33.70682
Adj.R-Squared	0.866071	S.D dependent Var	20.28203
S.E Regression	195.6168	Akaike Infor Criterion	7.22851
Sum Squared Resid	1334.641	Schwartz Infor Criterion	7.37729
Log Likelihood	-76.37577	Hannan-Quin Criterion	7.26356
F-Statistic	78.63500	Durbin-Watson Statistic	1.9717
Prob(Stat)	0.00000		

Table 4.1 above presents the ARDL test results for the effect of security condition on educational spending in Nigeria. The results indicated that budgetary allocation to education in the previous period had significant positive effect on education at less than 5% level of significance. Security had no significant effect at 5% level of significance. The R-Squared of 0.793693, shows that the model could explain 79% of the relationship between security situation and educational spending in Nigeria. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.12 indicated that the absence of auto-correlation.

Table 4.2 above presents the ARDL test results for the effect of security spending/condition on the performance of agriculture in Nigeria. The results indicated that expenditure on security and defense had significant negative effect at less than 5% level of significance on agricultural GDP in Nigeria. Agricultural output in the previous period had significant positive effect on agriculture. The model explains 89% of the relationship. Both the lag in the first period in agricultural output (agric (-1)) and security jointly explained the relationship between the dependent and independent variables according to F- statistic result. The D-W statistic indicated that there was no case of auto correlation. Tables 4.3 and 4.4, indicated that the poverty level (per capita) in the previous periods (percapita(-1)) had significant positive effect on poverty level in the reviewed periods. Security situation in the previous periods had significant negative effect on the poverty level in Nigeria. The model explains 91 % of the relationship between poverty level and security situation. The F statistic was significant at less than 5% level of significance. There was no case of auto correlation in the relationship. The result in table 4.4 indicated that poverty level had significant positive effect on the level of insecurity in Nigeria. The model explains 93% of the relationship between security situation and poverty in Nigeria. The F-statistic was significant at less than 5% level of significance. There was no case of auto correlation.

5.0 Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary: government expenditures on security had no significant effect on education in Nigeria. Security situation in Nigeria had significant negative effect on agriculture resulting in food scarcity, hunger and worsening poverty. For instance, the study indicated that sustained level of insecurity has continued to depress income per capita to worsen poverty level. The study indicated that worsening poverty is the major cause of insecurity in Nigeria. **Conclusion:** Security challenges remain the bane of sustainable development in Nigeria. It influences both the political and economic life of Nigeria. It may tear the country apart. The level of insecurity is the root cause of poverty, food scarcity and demand pressure. **Recommendations:** good governance still lacks in Africa. Majority of African leaders are more oppressive and regressive than the colonial rulers. Bad governance has continued to cause conflict, internal and interstate contradictions. Such governance does not create wealth and employment, but promotes conflict, corruption, starvation, hunger and poverty that result in insecurity and huge expenditures on security. Hence, there is need for good governance in Nigeria. The future of Nigeria politically and economically depends on political and security reforms. Just as the US champions the crusade against the scourge of terrorism and HIV/AIDS, Nigeria and Nigerians should take the issue of political reforms seriously. Nigeria should embark on conscientious peace-building that will promote justice, equity and fairness. There must proper reorientation of youths over the issues of ethno –religious matters, if Nigeria must continue to remain, as one country. Government must devise means of engaging its youths, if not insecurity would frustrate every effort by Nigeria to accomplish SDGs among other recommendations.

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